

01

Use case

Actors; ■ Director ■ Cameraman ■ Pilot Assist Drone AiRT

Scene 1

Day before the filming of the main scene of the film, the director, the Cameraman and the Pilot Assist meet at the stage chosen to prepare the filming.

Scene 2

AiRT is ready, the application shows at the top of the window a timeline, which indicates sequentially the necessary steps to reach the final flight. At the moment the timeline runs to the first milestone indicating that the equipment is ready, waiting to comply with the next step that will be the calibration

Scene 3

The timeline of the AiRT application marks that the calibration milestone has been reached and is ready for the reconstruction of the interior space.

Scene 5

The pilot has already made two full flights in the first two levels of height, only the last level remains to be filmed.

Scene 4

Now you've got the indoor map, now it's up to you the creative part, hahaha. Look! It is very easy to design the flight plan, you have two options. The first is drawing with your finger the path in both the vertical and horizontal planes, and in the points you can define some parameter of both the flight and the camera. Or another option is to mark the points and then joining them. Each point you mark will ask you to specify basic flight data and camera. If you also want to indicate some extra parameter you can add them. It is very intuitive!

Scene 6

The timeline of the AiRT application marks that it has reached the milestone of 3D reconstruction of the indoor space. The team is enthusiastic and eager to start working on the definition of the shots. They look and move through the virtual interior space through the different supports (FPV, mobile, Tablet ...), imagining what flight path they will perform.

Actors; ■ Director ■ Cameraman

Scene 7

1 Before designing your flight plans, I advise you to open a user account. This is optional, but it is very useful and important. It allows you to create a user, which you can access from anywhere you have installed the AiRT software, it is even compatible with other platforms. It allows sharing flight plans, mapping, filming ..., connecting to social networks, ... and also records your real and virtual flight hours and offers statistics linked to your skill in maneuvers and control of the equipment. It is really very useful, there is already a large community, and many users share their work.

2 Great, so each of us will open an account, and for the moment we share the files between us and so each one works from his account. What do you think?

Screenplay: author Virginia Santamarina (Universitat Politècnica de València)
 StoryBoards: authors Virginia Santamarina (Universitat Politècnica de València) & Ricardo Roca (S&R Communication)

3 For me this is fine. I also want to have a control of the flight hours.

The Pilot Assist explains to the director and Cameraman how they should use the interface and the importance of opening a user account in the AiRT community, which is associated with a multiplatform file hosting service in the cloud where they all the resources and uses developed can be stored and shared with AiRT. So before going to work to a specific place they can check if someone else has already worked in that place and ask to share files with them.

Scene 9

1 I do not know what happens, I already marked the path and points and the dots keep blinking in red, telling me that I still have not finished!

2 Look if you place your finger on the points a menu is displayed with the basic data you have to tell the system. It does not know where to go, but it does not know if it has to go fast, slowly stopping a few seconds ... This option also help you to modify the point in the two shots, for example, if you prefer to move the drone down a few centimeters.

4 Press on the points again, you will see that the icon "+" appears on the left, if you touch it, different options will be displayed ... flight, gimbal, photography, video ... with submenus for example in photography you have: focus, diaphragm, Colour temperature ..., choose the one you want to add and specify the data.

3 Okay, now I have all the points in green, but I also want to control the opening of the diaphragm, the exposure time, whether I want photos in a burst mode or not, at each point ..., how do I do this?

5 Ooooh, it's amazing!

The director and the Cameraman have already designed their flight plans using a Tablet and a mobile. But the application sends a warning messages that the plan is not completed and that they must specify more data, the timeline has not yet marked that the next milestone is achieved.

Scene 8

1 I have a problem: in this section I want to detail the parameters in centimeters, but I can not put the points with my fingers so close, what shall I do?

2 You can increase and decrease the indoor map, so you can work practically on a real scale.

3 Perfect! I have already found the magnifying glass, it can also be increased and decreased by opening or closing your fingers on the screen.

The director and the Cameraman, work on the design of the flight plan, they change from the vertical plane to the horizontal, modifying the points and adjusting them. They continuously reproduce the designed flight plan, visualizing the movement of the drone inside, or visualizing the image that would capture the camera.

Scene 10

2 It's true! It alerts me that in this section I should slow down because the maneuver is complicated. What shall I do?

1 If you have a closer look, although all the points of your plan are in green, at this point you can see a caution sign, if you press on it you will know what happens

3 You have two options, accept the suggestion and slow down, or reject the suggestion and maintain your flight plan. Whenever you do not get a message of high danger, these are only suggestions to improve the quality of your flight and filming. Once these issues are resolved, the timeline bar will mark 'completed flight plan'.

The director has already designed his flight plan, no red dots appear, all the points of the route are green, however, the timeline has not moved, and indicates that there is a problem.

Actors; ■ Director ■ Cameraman ■ Pilot Assist Drone AiRT

Scene 11

1 I think it's more important to film first, and at the same time as we are filming, we can take advantage and take your photos.

2 But the frames, I am looking for are different than yours

3 You have the possibility to merge flight plans, and the AiRT application returns you an option which shows the merged plan of both. Why won't you try this?

4 Ok, we will merge both, we fly all three options and then we will decide.

The timeline of the AiRT application marks that the milestone of the flight plan has been reached. The director and the Cameraman, have already designed their flight plans and have added all the details for a perfect and fully controlled filming, but both want their flight to be the first on the set because they want to capture the spontaneity of the children.

Scene 12

1 I prefer 100% automatic flight, and then study the routes and planes in the virtual space, and rectify what is convenient.

2 Uff I don't. I prefer automatic but with the option to modify the flight plan and movement of the gimbal.

3 No problem everything can be done. And if you want to, now that I understand what paths you want to perform, I propose that you fly without a flight plan. We record the path and you save it. Then we will see what you'll think about it.

They already have their flight plans ready (plan 1 of the director and plan 2 of the Cameraman), including the merged version (plan 3). Now it only remains to fly, but everyone wants to do it a different way.

Scene 13

1 Let's start with plan 1, this will be fine, first use the fully automatic flight, to focus on what the camera captures, then plan 2, the merged one and finally I make a manual flight and save it. You will have enough material to work this afternoon in the office on the perfect shot.

2 Sounds good to me, what shall I do?

3 Go to the flight tab, select your plan, then indicate the flight mode, which in your case will be automatic, and finally specify what you want to do with the saved images: where you want them to be sent, in which format ... Don't worry. Later these parameters can be changed during the flight.

4 Done! And the timeline has advanced to "ready to fly"! Now I get a warning message of the security measures and if I fulfill them, press the take-off button that appears now in the centre of the screen.

5 Very good. Well, let's go back a couple of meters and press the button.

The timeline has stopped in the flight plan, waiting for input, what plan and mode of flight is going to be chosen.

Scene 14

1 Let's go with plan 2, if you think it would be wise that as we have seen that at this point in the flight the drone has difficulties. You could try to modify trajectory or slow down, what do you think?

2 Okay, perfect, I'm going to try to correct some movement that I have now seen that they do not fit, and I also want to try playing with the gimbal.

3 Very well, in your case as you are not going to make an automatic flight, but you are going to use the automatic-assisted mode, in this tab you must indicate that what the drone must do after you modify your path, you have three options: 1st Return to the next point of the last point of the flight plan, the 2nd Return to the nearest point of the flight plan, or the 3rd option Return to the flight plan at a point freely chosen by the system. In addition, in the three options, you can indicate the radius of correction of the flight, if you want it to return to the point closest to 1 cm, to 2, 3 In this last option the system will not only find the nearest point, but optimize maneuver, reduce flight time ... Regarding gimbal, if you do not indicate otherwise, the gimbal will always rectify the movement to the point established in the plan.

4 Okay, all clear. I'll chose return to the nearest point of the plan. I already tells me "prepared to fly". I'll press the button take off on the screen.

The first flight plan of the director has been executed and everything has been perfect, but they detect that at the point where the system had already indicated that it was advisable to reduce the speed for that maneuver, the drone has made a very forced movement.

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Scene 15

1 Now we are going to make a manual flight, but as you will see in this mode I can also use the active safety measures. The IPS helps me to control the flight and the sensors prevent it from crashing against objects or people. It is also advisable to indicate the level of security that we need, for example, at what distance we allow the drone to approach to something. In this case I put that the drone will always keep a minimum distance of 20 cm from any static or dynamic obstacles. But, for example, when filming with the children I could indicate that in the "Z" axis it will not approach more than 50 cm.

2 That's great! How can you handle the drone so well?

3 Hahaha, if you want to go skilful this afternoon at the office just make a free flight in the virtual space of the factory, and you will see how you improve the control in a few hours of flight. It also might help you to find new flight paths and inspiration.

4 That's true! I will do so...

They have already made the 2nd flight plan from the Cameraman and the merged flight plan it with the automatic one. Now the Pilot Assist will make a last free flight, trying to collect the suggestions of the director and the Cameraman, so that they have 4 flight options to work with.

Scene 16

1 I recommend you to analyze calmly the four flight options this afternoon.

2 But then ... we have to opt for one of the shots?

3 No, you do not have to decide for one, in fact, you have the possibility to copy sections of a plan and paste it into another, or even start a new plan by copying and pasting points of all, and adding new ones. Then you can visualize the movement of the drone in a virtual space, and even visualize the actual images that the camera will display. Virtual images of the space will be shown in those sections, where you have added new points and frames, in case that you do not have real images.

4 Ahhh! And how do we paste and copy from one plan to another?

5 You will see that it is very simple, the interface is very intuitive, when you indicate new flight plan, you have a multi-window option. The app allows to open up to 4 windows in mosaic simultaneously. In each window you open the plan that you want, and you keep a window for the new plan in case you want to design it again from zero. Then you just have to cut and paste the exact points you want, or drag with your finger each point from one window to another window.

6 But ... and if we can not stick them at the same point?

7 Don't worry, it detects the exact position and tells you where to put it when you change the windows, but you can also disable this option and place the points freely.

All pre-filming flights have already been made and recorded, now the film crew has a lot of material to analyze the paths. And even design and visualize new proposals in the virtual space. Now they have a lot of work, but in the office...

Scene 17

1 I see that you've put yourself the biggest screen in the office, and ... you've been flying for 2 hours! And you've crashed it only once! Hahahaha! What? Now you want to get the title of pilot? Hahaha...

2 Hahaha, I really wanted to know all the options of maneuvering and shots. And, the truth is, connecting the remote control to the computer is just great! You really have the impression to fly. I already have very clear the trajectory. It does not differ very much from what we had before, but the simulator allowed me to know better the space, especially to define very well all the movements of the camera

3 Do you have the other remote control of the equipment, so I can test it on the other computer?

4 No, I think they have taken it already, but you can use also the Tablet to fly. Have a look at this! Open the program on the computer and on the tablet, link the two devices and on the tablet you will see the function 'remote control'! The screen becomes a touch screen remote control.

5 That's great! For those who do not know how to fly, this seems to be easier, isn't it?

6 Yes, it is more intuitive, but I prefer to use the remote control.

The Cameraman is in the office, he has the whole afternoon to analyze the flight plans and to decide which option suits more. He wants to have the camera trajectory completely closed, since the next day he will have a very limited shooting time. So everything has to be perfect. He knows that working with such young children has a limited time to shoot, and also if he wants to film in the blue hour, time is very short. The software has been installed on several computers in the office, so that several people can work simultaneously.

Scene 18

1 Open "new flight plan" and indicate multi-window option. So we can choose from which projects we want to work.

2 Ok, so I leave an empty window for the new project and in the other three I open the ones that are our interest.

3 I have a doubt, so we can only use three projects? Because ... the fourth window is occupied by the new one?

4 In fact, it only lets you to have 3 open at the same time and the new one. But you can extract what you are interested from one, then close and open another different project.

5 Ahhh, so if you agree, we can open the merged flight plan from this morning, the one you've done right now, and also the first one made by the Pilot Assist.

The Cameraman and the director, have already clear the trajectories of the drone and the camera movements. They decide to sit together and together they draw the new flight plan.

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Scene 19

1 I think, the best would be to do two different projects, one for filming and another one for photography. By modifying only the specifications of the camera, the frames can be maintained. What do you think?

2 Perfect, if you want to first we may make the flight plan for filming and when we have defined the movements of the camera, we will do the same for the photography. We have two options or manually indicate the movement of the camera at each point, or select the movement options offered by the program that are quite complete.

3 But if we select the default movements, can we modify them during the filming?

4 Of course! Like any flight option, you can rectify and modify during the shoot.

5 Perfect! Well, let's have a look. I would like to start with a very dynamic shot with the background far away, but not the children. So to say a travelling compensated with a zoom.

6 Ok, so click on the first point "camera movement", then "traveling" and finally click on "travelling zoom", then indicate the amplitude of the movement, so to say the point at which you want that movement.

The Cameraman and the director are working together on the design of the new flight plan. They have already completed it, so they have only to specify the movements and specifications of the camera.

Scene 20

1 In the case of photography, the same happens with the movements of the camera. You can select different modes of photography or you can specify manually at each point what type of photo you would like to get.

2 Could you also select a shooting mode and then manually change the parameters before the flight?

3 Yes, of course, even during the flight. Look, for example, at this point it is just when the children spin around the column with the hand, ... I indicate "photography", then select "creative mode", and then I add: portrait, speed and indoor. Now I can deploy the specifications and change the shutter speed, aperture, white balance, ...

The Cameraman and the director, have already specified all the movements of the camera. They have also a very precise flight plan for filming. Now they have just to duplicate the project and repeat a new version for the photographic shots.

Scene 21

1 The first thing that we are going to do is to show the children the trajectory they follow. While they run we will lift up the drone in the air, so that the children see how it works and get familiarized. We will take a test shot to see how the drone coordinates with the speed of the children.

2 And ... if I jump can I touch the drone?

3 Not because he's a very shy drone, and if you get close to him he'll just fly away, do you want to see him?

4 Yeeeeees.

The day of shooting has come and everything is ready. The anchors have been placed, the drone is located in the take-off area near the beginning of the trajectory. The director and the Cameraman have already indicated to the Pilot Assist the flight plan they want to realize for the filming and photo shooting. The stylist and makeup artist have already prepared the children. The director explains to the children that when they hear "5 and action" they must count in silence until five before running, so that the drone has enough time to follow them.

Scene 22

1 Quiet on the set!

2 Roll camera!

3 Five...and action!

4 This shot is perfect for a photo, I did not realize it, in the next shot I will make the photo manually.

5 It's true! It is a perfect shot, especially if we get that light stays the same.

El director se sienta frente a un portátil para controlar la toma y la coordinación de los niños y el dron. La persona encargada de dar la claqueta anuncia la secuencia, plano y toma y hace un fuerte chack, tras oír la orden de "graba" del Cameraman. The children already know the meandering they have to do between the columns, and have become familiar with the drone. They have already made a complete tour accompanied by the drone. They enter the blue hour, and they have only about 30 minutes to film and take the photos. The Cameraman is prepared and does not take the gaze of the Tablet from which he controls the gimbal and the camera. The director sits in front of a laptop to control the shots and coordination of the children and the drone. The person in charge of the clapperboard announces the sequence, and sharp 'clap', after hearing the order of "roll camera" of the Cameraman.

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Scene 23

The shot has been perfect, the children have run between the columns with great energy and in perfect coordination with the drone. Now we have to repeat the scene to take the pictures. With only 10 minutes of blue hour remaining, the Pilot Assist quickly changes the batteries of the AiRT drone and checks that everything is correct. The director reminds the children how important it is that they repeat exactly the same course at the same speed.

Scene 24

In the second shot, the children have repeated the same course, but they have gone a little slower, so the Pilot Assist has corrected the speed of the drone and everything has been perfect.

Scene 25

The Cameraman has edited a fragment of 15 seconds and uploaded it to both the social networks and the AiRT community. The feedback has been very fast.